

Power Control in Vehicle-to-Vehicle Networks: A Static Geometric Programming Reformulation

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Abstract

This report presents a static geometric programming (GP) reformulation of the power control and computation offloading problem in vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) platoon networks. Building upon the dynamic optimization model originally proposed by Wang et al., the dynamic task allocation and time-dependent variables are eliminated, enabling a computationally efficient static GP framework that preserves essential network constraints, such as signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) requirements and local processing capabilities. The reformulated model captures the trade-off between local processing power and transmission power under cumulative interference as the platoon length increases. Simulation results demonstrate that the GP-based approach provides feasible and scalable solutions for varying platoon sizes, while maintaining required SINR thresholds and minimizing total power consumption. Moreover, the results highlight the nonlinear growth in power demand and solver time as the number of platoon members increases, illustrating the practical trade-offs between energy efficiency, system scalability, and interference management. This work provides a foundation for future extensions, including probabilistic outage modeling and cooperative processing among vehicles, to further enhance the adaptability and realism of power control strategies in V2V networks.

1 Original Problem Formulation and Background

In Wang, Liang, and Zhao [1], the authors propose a system optimization model for joint computation offloading and power allocation (COPA) scheme along with a multiagent deep deterministic policy gradient (DDGP) with a non-convex optimization problem referred to as the Power Decision-Making Problem (PDMP), which aims to minimize both energy consumption and computation offloading.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the platoon network model (adapted from [1]).

The platoon configuration is illustrated in Fig. 1. The optimal power allocation for each vehicle, obtained by solving the PDMP, is subsequently used as input to a neural network to support decision-making optimization. The PDMP optimization problem is formulated as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underset{\mathbf{p}}{\text{minimize}} && \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T [\omega_1 \vartheta_1 E(t) + \omega_2 \vartheta_2 Q(t)] && (1) \\
 & \text{subject to} && 0 \leq p_{m,l} \leq p_{m,l}^{\max} \quad \forall t \in T && (1a) \\
 & && 0 \leq p_{m,o} \leq p_{m,o}^{\max} \quad \forall t \in T && (1b) \\
 & && 0 \leq p_{0,m} \leq p_{0,m}^{\max} \quad \forall t \in T. && (1c)
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, $E(t)$ represents the average energy consumption of the platoon system, while $Q(t)$ denotes the average buffer queue length. The sets M and T represent the platoon members ($m \in M$) and time slots ($t \in T$), respectively.

The decision variables are defined as follows: $p_{m,l}$ represents the local computing power (the processing capacity in each vehicle) allocated to each platoon member (PM) m ; $p_{m,o}$ denotes the transmission power allocated by PM m for offloading tasks to the PL; and $p_{0,m}$ captures the processing power dedicated by the PL (platoon leader) to execute the offloaded tasks (or process the offloaded data) received from PM m . Constraints (1a), (1b), and (1c) ensure that the allocated power values do not exceed their respective maximum limits. The weighting coefficients ω_1 and ω_2 balance the trade-off between energy consumption and task execution latency of the platoon system. Similarly, ϑ_1 and ϑ_2 represent the per-unit cost of energy consumption and buffer queue length, respectively.

$E(t)$ and $Q(t)$ are formulated as:

$$E(t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M (p_{m,l}(t) \cdot \tau_0 + p_{m,o}(t) \cdot t_{m,off}(t) + p_{0,m}(t) \cdot (\tau_0 - t_{m,off}(t))). \quad (2)$$

$$Q(t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M Q_m(t). \quad (3)$$

where

τ_0 : time-slot duration.

$t_{m,off}$: task data transmission time of PM m .

$Q_m(t)$: represent the the current length of buffer queue.

For each PM m , considering a descending order of signal strength, the SINR (signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio, or SIR as we studied from Kandukuri and Boyd [2]) at a time-slot t is defined as follow:

$$\zeta_m(t) = \frac{p_{m,o} \cdot h_m^2(t)}{\sigma^2 + I_m(t)}. \quad (4)$$

The interference experienced by PM m is given by

$$I_m = \sum_i p_{i,o}(t)(h_i(t))^2, \quad (5)$$

where $p_{i,o}(t)(h_i(t))^2 \leq p_{m,o}(t)(h_m(t))^2$.

The channel gain between PM m and the PL at time-slot t is expressed as

$$h_m(t) = g_0 \cdot (d_{m,0}(t))^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot n_0(t). \quad (6)$$

where g_0 is the channel power gain at 1-m reference distance, α is the path-loss exponent, and $n_0(t) \in \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$.

2 Convexity Analysis and Geometric Programming Reformulation

The optimization problem formulated in (1) is inherently non-convex, primarily due to the time-averaging over an infinite horizon, the presence of a logarithmic function in the data transmission rate, and additional nonlinearities. Our objective is to determine whether the problem can be reformulated as a convex optimization problem using **geometric programming (GP)**. If a valid GP formulation is feasible, we will benchmark its performance against the original problem and analyze the resulting outcomes.

3 Dynamic to Static Optimization Reformulation

A standard **Geometric Programming (GP)** problem is formulated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & f_0(\cdot) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & f_i(\cdot) \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, m \\ & g_j(\cdot) = 1, \quad j = 1, \dots, p \end{aligned}$$

where $f_0(\cdot)$ and $f_i(\cdot)$ are posynomials, which are sums of monomial terms, and $g_j(\cdot)$ are monomials.

This condition implies that a GP formulation is valid only if all constraints and the objective function can be expressed as monomials or posynomials. However, the presence of temporal dependencies -such as time-slots, system history, or variable updates between iterations-can introduce non-posynomial equations, which violate GP constraints.

Since a GP formulation is most suitable for static environments, we reformulate the original problem in a static setting, where the channel conditions remain constant over time and designing-solving the problem in a time t would not change the interference over time. In this static framework, each PM m in the platoon determines its power transmission and processing power based on a single 'snapshot' of the system, meaning that the power control optimization is solved only once rather than iteratively over time.

4 GP Reformulation of the Optimization Problem

In the static model, all variables that explicitly depend on time are excluded. Since the reformulated geometric program is solved only once and no buffering mechanism is modeled, the task queue variable $Q(t)$ becomes irrelevant and is therefore omitted from the objective function. Furthermore, this static formulation assumes that the platoon leader (PL) has sufficient computing capacity to process all offloaded tasks without introducing additional constraints or the need to transmit results back to the platoon members (PMs). Consequently, the variable $p_{0,m}$, which would otherwise represent the computing power allocated by the PL to process the data transmitted from the PMs, plays no role in this scenario. As a result, the only decision variables are $p_{m,l}$ and $p_{m,o}$, which represent the local computing and transmission powers for each PM, respectively.

The original problem sought to jointly optimize energy consumption and processing time. To preserve this objective within the static GP framework, we introduce constraints that enforce task completion by bounding both local computing performance and transmission capacity. We also enforce a constraint on the SINR, which, unlike in the dynamic formulation, is now fixed for each optimization instance.

Let γ_m denote the SINR threshold. As shown in Section 4.1 of Boyd et al. [3], the SINR constraint can be expressed as a polysynomial:

$$\frac{\sigma^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} p_{i,o} h_i^2}{p_{m,o} h_m^2} \leq \frac{1}{\gamma_m}. \quad (7)$$

In this model, the local computing rate (and power) is controlled by $p_{m,l}$, while the offloaded portion of the workload depends on the transmission power $p_{m,o}$ and the resulting SINR. To ensure that the entire workload is processed, either locally or remotely, we require that the sum of the local processing rate and the offloading rate satisfies the total task arrival rate λ_m . According to equation (10) in Wang, Liang, and Zhao [1] and using Shannon's capacity theorem in Stanford University, Lecture 7 [4], we can express the transmission rate from PM m to the PL as:

$$r_m = B \log_2(1 + \gamma_m), \quad (8)$$

where B is the channel bandwidth. On the other hand, equation (11) in Wang, Liang, and Zhao [1] defines the local processing rate as:

$$\frac{f_m}{L_0} \cdot \tau_0,$$

where f_m is the local computing frequency, given by the power-frequency relationship:

$$f_m = \left(\frac{p_{m,l}}{\kappa_m} \right)^{1/3}. \quad (9)$$

Intuitively, the total service rate must be at least equal to the task arrival rate:

$$\frac{f_m}{L_0} + \frac{r_m}{L_0} \geq \lambda_m.$$

The issue is that this inequality is not GP-compatible (or at least it does not follow the disciplined geometric programming rules in CVXPY). Although the left-hand side can be simplified by factoring out L_0 , the sum of two monomials is not a posynomial, and therefore not admissible in a geometric program. A careful reformulation of the problem is required to ensure that all inequalities satisfy the disciplined geometric programming (DGP) rules, as defined in the CVXPY documentation.

To resolve this, we introduce an auxiliary parameter $\bar{\lambda}_m$, which represents the offloaded portion of the task data rate. The locally processed portion is thus given by $\lambda_m - \bar{\lambda}_m$. This separation enables a GP-compatible decomposition, in which the two rates, the transmission rate r_m and the local processing rate f_m , are modeled via separate constraints. For instance, if $\lambda_m = 6$ Mbps and $\bar{\lambda}_m = 2$ Mbps, then the PM processes 4 Mbps locally and offloads the remaining 2 Mbps to the PL.

This decomposition allows us to formulate distinct constraints for local computing and transmission. Since the static model excludes temporal variables, we remove the τ_0 factor. Combining the power-frequency relationship with the inequality $\frac{f_m}{L_0} \geq \lambda_m - \bar{\lambda}_m$, and raising both sides to the power of three, we obtain the monomial constraint:

$$p_{m,l} \geq \kappa_m [L_0(\lambda_m - \bar{\lambda}_m)]^3. \quad (10)$$

This constraint ensures that the allocated local power $p_{m,l}$ is sufficient to process the locally handled data. Due to the cubic dependence, the local power requirement grows rapidly with the amount of data processed on-board.

On the transmission side, the offloaded rate $\bar{\lambda}_m$ must be fully transmitted during the same optimization instance. Since no buffer is assumed, the SINR must be large enough to support this transmission rate. Using Shannon's formula in Stanford University, Lecture 7 [4], the following condition must hold:

$$B \log_2(1 + \gamma_m) \geq \bar{\lambda}_m,$$

which can be rewritten as:

$$\gamma_m \geq 2^{\bar{\lambda}_m/B} - 1. \quad (11)$$

This expression defines the minimum SINR required to offload $\bar{\lambda}_m$ Mbps. As such, the transmission power $p_{m,o}$ must be chosen to achieve this SINR, satisfying the constraint in equation (7).

The trade-off between local processing and offloading plays a critical role in determining power allocation strategies. When the offloaded data rate $\bar{\lambda}_m$ is small, the majority of the computational workload is handled locally, which increases the demand for local processing power $p_{m,l}$ while reducing the need for transmission power $p_{m,o}$. Conversely, when $\bar{\lambda}_m$ is large, a greater portion of the workload is transmitted to the platoon leader (PL), shifting the resource burden to the communication channel. This scenario requires a higher SINR and, consequently, may lead to increased transmission power $p_{m,o}$.

In the limiting case where $\bar{\lambda}_m = \lambda_m$, the entire workload is offloaded, resulting in no local processing. This would theoretically allow $p_{m,l} = 0$. However, such a scenario is neither practical nor desirable, as all vehicles are assumed to have a minimum local processing capability. This implies that λ_m will be always greater than $\bar{\lambda}_m$.

5 Static GP formulation

Let $\mathbf{P} = \{p_{m,l}, p_{m,o}\}$ denote the set of decision variables. The static model is reformulated as a Geometric Program (GP) by eliminating time-dependent variables from the objective function, incorporating constraints given in equations (7) and (10), and enforcing the power limit constraints.

Before solving the optimization problem, we establish a lower bound for the SINR threshold to ensure that the offloaded data rate is sufficient. This requirement is imposed as a precondition rather than an explicit constraint within the optimization model, reducing problem complexity and improving computational efficiency, being this condition the equation (10):

$$\gamma_m \geq 2^{\frac{\bar{\lambda}_m}{B}} - 1.$$

By treating γ_m as a parameter defined by the optimization problem, we guarantee that the computed power allocations meet the minimum SINR requirement without increasing the optimization problem's dimensionality.

There is a particular case in which equation fails to satisfy the GP-compatibility conditions, and this occurs when the offloaded data rate is $\bar{\lambda}_m = 0$. Under these conditions, the lower bound for the SINR threshold becomes:

$$\gamma_m \geq 2^{\frac{0}{B}} - 1 = 2^0 - 1 = 1 - 1 = 0 \implies \gamma_m \geq 0.$$

This result implies that γ_m could take the value of zero, which is physically meaningless in the context of SINR, as it must be -and we want it to be- strictly positive. Moreover, substituting $\gamma_m = 0$ into constraint (7) would lead to a division by zero, undefining the problem and violating the requirements of geometric programming.

To address this issue, we introduce a lower bound for the SINR threshold to ensure both physical consistency and GP-compatibility. Let $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$ be a small positive constant used to prevent γ_m from reaching zero. We then define the minimum SINR threshold as:

$$\gamma_m = \max \left(2^{\frac{\bar{\lambda}_m}{B}} - 1, \epsilon \right). \quad (12)$$

This modification guarantees that γ_m is always strictly positive, thereby preserving the feasibility and structure of the geometric program.

The objective of the optimization problem is to minimize the total power consumption across all platoon members, subject to constraints on SINR, local computation capability, and power limits. Since the weights ω_1 and ϑ_1 introduced in the original formulation do not affect the structure or solution of the reformulated problem, they can be set to 1 without loss of generality. This simplification allows us to omit them from the model, leading to the following problem formulation:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \underset{\mathbf{P}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_{m=1}^M p_{m,l} + p_{m,o} \\
& \text{subject to} && \left(\frac{\sigma^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} p_{i,o} h_i^2}{p_{m,o} h_m^2} \right) \leq \frac{1}{\gamma_m}, \quad \forall m \in M, \\
& && \kappa_m [L_0 (\lambda_m - \bar{\lambda}_m)]^3 \leq p_{m,l}, \quad \forall m \in M, \\
& && p_{m,l} \leq p_{m,l}^{\max}, \quad \forall m \in M, \\
& && p_{m,o} \leq p_{m,o}^{\max}, \quad \forall m \in M.
\end{aligned}$$

All the constraints in the problem can be expressed as posynomial functions of the decision variables $p_{m,l}$ and $p_{m,o}$. The resulting GP formulation is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \underset{\mathbf{P}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_{m=1}^M p_{m,l} + p_{m,o} && (13) \\
& \text{subject to} && (\gamma_m) \left(\frac{\sigma^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} p_{i,o} h_i^2}{p_{m,o} h_m^2} \right) \leq 1, \quad \forall m \in M, && (13a) \\
& && \frac{\kappa_m [L_0 (\lambda_m - \bar{\lambda}_m)]^3}{p_{m,l}} \leq 1, \quad \forall m \in M, && (13b) \\
& && \frac{p_{m,l}}{p_{m,l}^{\max}} \leq 1, \quad \forall m \in M, && (13c) \\
& && \frac{p_{m,o}}{p_{m,o}^{\max}} \leq 1, \quad \forall m \in M. && (13d)
\end{aligned}$$

In **Section 8** the proposed base model is implemented using Python and the CVXPY library, which is designed for solving convex and disciplined geometric programming problems. The implementation is used to simulate multiple scenarios of interest, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the model under varying system parameters and operational conditions.

6 Results

The simulation experiments are run on a Laptop with an Intel Core i7-12650H CPU with 2.3 frequency. The graphics card is the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 Laptop GPU with 6-GB memory. The implementation and resolution of the geometric programming (GP) problem were carried out using Python 3.13 and CVXPY version 1.6.0.

Parameter	Value
Channel power gain at 1 meter g_0	$1e^{-4}$
Path loss exponent α	2
Bandwidth B	10 MHz
Gaussian white noise power σ^2	10^{-9} W
Maximum local computing power $p_{m,l}^{max}$	10^6 W
Maximum transmitting power $p_{m,o}^{max}$	10^6 W
Effective switch capacitance of PMs κ_m	10^{-27}
Amount of CPU cycles required for task computing L_0	1000
SINR threshold lower bound ϵ to avoid $\gamma_m = 0$	$1e^{-5}$
Distance between each EC Server-Transmitter pair d	10 m

Table 1. Summary of simulation parameters

The simulation uses the same parameter values as those presented in Wang, Liang, and Zhao [1], specifically those that do not depend on time. Minor modifications were introduced to adapt the model to a static setting, as summarized in Table 1.

In the simulation setup, all platoon members (PMs) transmit data exclusively to the platoon leader (PL). The initial distance between each EC server and transmitter pair is fixed at 10 meters. Each PM is assigned identical computing and transmission capabilities. Since the wireless channel conditions depend on the position of each PM relative to the PL, the channel gain and noise level vary accordingly. Consequently, the required transmission power differs across vehicles, depending on their respective distances to the PL, for a total of M vehicles in the platoon.

To ensure feasibility in the optimization process, a sufficiently large upper bound was set for both local computing and transmission power variables. This allows the optimization algorithm to adjust these variables flexibly in response to the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) constraints while minimizing total power consumption.

Fig. 2. Power distribution and SINR. M=5.

Fig. 3. Power distribution and SINR. M=7.

Fig. 4. Power distribution and SINR. M=9.

Fig. 5. Power distribution and SINR. $M=11$.

Figures 2 to 5 shows the evolution of power allocation and SINR across platoon members (PMs) for 5, 7, 9 and 11 vehicles ($M = 5$, $M = 7$, $M = 9$ and $M = 11$). Each figure show the local computing power, transmitting power, and achieved SINR for each vehicle in the platoon.

As the number of PMs increases, a clear trend emerges: the total interference accumulated by each vehicle grows due to additional simultaneous transmissions on the same channel, all directed toward the PL, from vehicles positioned further along the platoon. This increase in interference requires more transmission power $p_{m,o}$ to maintain the minimum SINR threshold, particularly for PMs that are more distant from the PL. Conversely, the local computing power $p_{m,l}$ remains stable across different values for M , since it depends primarily on the computing capacity of each vehicle and not on interference.

The SINR achieved by each vehicle remains consistently above the required threshold, confirming the feasibility of the optimization under all configurations. However, small deviations in the SINR profiles across vehicles are observed as a result of the interference increasing from PMs positioned further back in the platoon. These results highlight the trade-off between scalability and power efficiency. As M -total platoon members- increase, more transmission power is needed to counteract the rising interference, despite using the same offloading policy ($\bar{\lambda}_m = 2$ Mbps).

Fig. 6. Solve time and total power consumption for 2 to 20 vehicles (PMs) in the platoon.

Fig. 7. Solve time and total power consumption for 2 to 60 vehicles (PMs) in the platoon.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 presents the evolution of the total solving time and power consumption as the number of PMs increases from 2 to 20 and from 2 to 60, respectively. The left subplot shows the solver execution time, while the right subplot presents the corresponding total power consumption across all vehicles.

The solving time exhibits a gradual increase with respect to M . This could be due to the quadratic growth in the number of interference terms and constraints that must be evaluated for larger platoons. We can notice that at $M = 20$ the total solve time remains below 0.5 seconds, showing the computational efficiency of the GP-based formulation of the problem.

We can evidence that the total power consumption increases with the number of vehicles M , showing a exponential-like growth pattern. This trend reflects the cumulative demand for processing constraints for each platoon member. However, the increase is not strictly monotonic. Due to the optimization process, some compensation occurs through interference-aware resource allocation, which can reduce the transmission power requirements of vehicles positioned towards the front-positioned PMs (closer to the PL). In

contrast, the vehicles positioned towards the end of the platoon experience higher power demands, as they are subject to more accumulated interference from following vehicles.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of the solver execution time (left plot) and total power consumption (right plot) for a range of $M = 2$ to $M = 60$ vehicles or platoon members. The simulation uses a fixed data arrival rate of 6.0 Mbps per vehicle and an offloaded portion of 2.0 Mbps.

The left subplot reveals that the solving time increases approximately exponentially with M . For small platoon sizes (e.g., $M < 10$), the solve time remains below 0.1 seconds. However, as M grows, the number of optimization variables and SINR-related constraints increases quadratically, leading to a significant increase in computational complexity. Beyond $M = 40$, the solver time rises sharply, reaching over 4 seconds at $M = 60$, highlighting the limits of scalability for real-time applications under Geometric Programming formulations.

On the right, the total power consumption also exhibits exponential growth. This behavior results from the accumulation of both local computing and transmission power across all PMs, especially under growing interference and channel degradation in longer platoons. Although the GP solver efficiently allocates power to minimize energy usage under constraints, the increase in problem size and interference dominates the global trend.

These results demonstrate that while the GP formulation remains feasible and stable for up to 60 vehicles, its computational efficiency and energy scaling are nonlinear and sensitive to network size (M).

7 Future Research Directions

There are several potential directions that can build upon the current static formulation and serve as a foundation for further study and practical extensions.

- (a) In this work, we examined and simulated the case in which the PMs transmit directly and exclusively to the PL for offloading the portion of data that exceeds their local computing capacity, assuming that the PL has sufficient resources to process all received tasks. A valuable extension would be to consider heterogeneous PMs with varying local computing capacities and a PL with limited or finite computing resources. In this scenario, an efficient strategy could involve enabling the PL to transmit processed results back to selected PMs that have available capacity to continue processing tasks. This concept can be extended even further by exploring cooperative communication among PMs themselves: vehicles with surplus computing capacity could receive and process tasks from nearby PMs, thereby reducing overall transmission power and balancing resource usage more effectively.
- (b) Throughout our simulations, it was assumed that all PMs transmit to the PL over the same communication channel, which naturally results in interference among simultaneous transmissions. This assumption opens opportunities to study alternative platoon topologies and resource allocation strategies where certain PMs can

transmit without interfering with others, or where dynamic channel allocation techniques are applied to mitigate interference and improve overall system performance.

- (c) Complementary to the previous cases, it is particularly promising to extend the static model by incorporating an outage probability variable into the channel model. Introducing a probabilistic dimension to the system would allow the simulation of more realistic scenarios that account for statistical variations in both received signal power and interference levels. Such an approach would enhance the adaptability and robustness of the model, providing insights into the impact of channel uncertainty on power allocation and system feasibility.

8 Python Implementation

We implemented our optimization problem using Python and the CVXPY library as a solver for the GP problem. The implementation follows the Power Control example from CVXPY Developers [5] as a reference for structuring the GP formulation. The full implementation used to generate the results (for M vehicles) is provided here.

```

1 import cvxpy as cp
2 import numpy as np
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 import matplotlib.ticker as ticker
5 import time
6
7 # Parameters
8 M = 5 # Number of vehicles in the platoon
9 lambda_m = 6e6 # Total data [bps]
10 lambda_bar_m = 2e6 # Offloaded data [bps]
11 B = 10e6 # Bandwidth [Hz]
12 p_max_l = 1000.0 # Max. local computing power [W]
13 p_max_o = 1000.0 # Max. transmitting power [W]
14 kappa_m = 1e-28 # Effective switched capacitance (PM)
15 L0 = 1000 # CPU cycles per bit
16 g0 = 1e-4 # Channel gain at 1 meter
17 alpha = 2.0 # Path loss exponent
18 sigma2 = 1e-9 # Noise power (-174dBm/Hz * B) [W]
19 epsilon = 1e-5 # SINR threshold lower bound (to avoid gamma_m =
    0)
20 d = 10 # Distances between each PM from the PL [m]
21
22 # Distances from PM m to the PL
23 distances = np.array([(m+1)*d for m in range(M)])
24
25 # Channel gains
26 h_m = g0 * ((distances)**(-alpha/2))
27
28 # Problem definition
29 p_l = cp.Variable(M, pos=True) # Local computing power
30 p_o = cp.Variable(M, pos=True) # Transmitting power
31 gamma = cp.Variable(M, pos=True) # SINR
32
33 # Objective function
34 objective = cp.Minimize(cp.sum(p_l + p_o))
35

```

```

36 # Constraints
37 constraints = []
38 for m in range(M):
39     # Interference
40     interference = sigma2 + cp.sum([p_o[i] * h_m[i]**2 for i in range(m
+1, M)])
41
42     # SINR
43     constraints += [
44         (interference / (p_o[m] * h_m[m]**2)) * gamma[m] <= 1,
45         gamma[m] >= max(2**(lambda_bar_m/B) - 1, epsilon) # Avoid gamma
=0
46     ]
47
48     # Local processing and power constraints
49     constraints += [
50         p_l[m] >= kappa_m * (L0 * (lambda_m - lambda_bar_m))**3,
51         p_l[m] <= p_max_l,
52         p_o[m] <= p_max_o
53     ]
54
55 # Verify DGP
56 problem = cp.Problem(objective, constraints)
57 print("Is DGP?", problem.is_dgp())
58
59 # Solving
60 start_time = time.time()
61 problem = cp.Problem(objective, constraints)
62 problem.solve(gp=True)
63 solve_time = time.time() - start_time
64
65 # Status
66 print(f"\nSolution status: {problem.status}")
67
68 # Results
69 print(f"Solving time: {solve_time:.4f} seconds")
70
71 power_data = {
72     "Local": p_l.value,
73     "Transmitting": p_o.value,
74     "Total": p_l.value + p_o.value
75 }
76
77 sinr_target = 2**(lambda_bar_m/B) - 1
78 sinr_achieved = [(p_o[m].value * h_m[m]**2) /
79     (sigma2 + sum(p_o[i].value * h_m[i]**2 for i in range(m
+1, M)))]
80     for m in range(M)]
81
82 # Graphs
83 plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
84
85 # Power variables
86 plt.subplot(1, 2, 1)
87 x = np.arange(M)
88 plt.bar(x - 0.2, power_data["Local"], 0.4, label='Local')
89 plt.bar(x + 0.2, power_data["Transmitting"], 0.4, label='Transmitting')
90 plt.xticks(x, [f"{i+1}" for i in range(M)])

```

```

91 plt.xlabel("Vehicles")
92 plt.ylabel("Power (W)")
93 plt.title(f"Power Distribution of each vehicle (M={M}) \nTotal data: {
    lambda_m/1000000:.1f} Mbps, Offloaded data: {lambda_bar_m/1000000:.1f
    } Mbps")
94 plt.legend()
95
96 # SINR
97 plt.subplot(1, 2, 2)
98 plt.plot(sinr_achieved, 'bo-', label='Accomplished')
99 plt.xticks(range(M), [f"{i+1}" for i in range(M)])
100 plt.xlabel("Vehicle")
101 plt.ylabel("SINR")
102 plt.title(f"SINR of each vehicle (M={M}) \nTotal data: {lambda_m/1e6:.1f
    } Mbps, Offloaded data: {lambda_bar_m/1e6:.1f} Mbps")
103 plt.gca().yaxis.set_major_formatter(ticker.ScalarFormatter(useMathText=
    True))
104 plt.gca().yaxis.set_minor_formatter(ticker.NullFormatter())
105 plt.ticklabel_format(style='plain', axis='y')
106 plt.legend()
107
108 plt.tight_layout()
109 plt.show()
110
111 # Results table
112 from tabulate import tabulate
113
114 table = []
115 for m in range(M):
116     table.append([
117         m+1,
118         f"{distances[m]} m",
119         f"{power_data['Local'][m]:.4f} W",
120         f"{power_data['Transmitting'][m]:.4f} W",
121         f"{sinr_achieved[m]:.4f}"
122     ])
123
124 print("\nDetailed results for each vehicle:")
125 print(tabulate(table,
126     headers=["Veh cle", "Distance", "Local P.", "P.
    Transmitting", "SINR"],
127     tablefmt="grid"))

```

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